

Cultural Terms in Need Analysis of English for Tour Guiding

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Abstract

Tour guides have an important role in conveying information about tourist destinations, including cultural aspects which are an integral part of the tourist experience. This research aims to develop speaking teaching materials that focus on understanding cultural vocabularies for preparing students as tour guides. This research is development type of research using ADDIE model to produce English teaching materials in Tourism Department. The model consists of five steps, namely: (1) analysis (analysis), (2) design, (3) development (development), (4) implementation and (5) evaluation. The data were collected through questionnaire, interview and observation. The questionnaire was distributed to 120 students in Tourism Department, meanwhile the interview conducted to three English lecturers. The data obtained from distributed questionnaire was used for need analysis and showed that the student's demands to develop speaking ability because of the materials provide limited cultural vocabularies. Meanwhile, the result of evaluation was indicated the development of speaking teaching materials with a focus on understanding cultural terms can significantly improve the communication skills of students in Tourism Department. The resulting teaching material is not only more focused and relevant, but is also able to provide a richer and more focused tourist experience.

1. Introduction

Tourism has an important role in the economy of a region, and in this context, Bali has become a major tourist destination known for its natural beauty, cultural heritage and unique traditions

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(Suweta 2020). Tour guides play a key role in conveying information to tourists, including in regarding local culture. One of the crucial aspects in communicating effectively about culture is understanding vocabulary related to aspects of that culture (Nurazizah 2021).

Balinese culture has a unique richness in the form of dance, art, traditional ceremonies and other traditions. However, there are challenges in conveying cultural information authentically and engagingly for tourists, especially if the tour guide does not have an adequate understanding of Cultural terms (Subhiksu and Utama 2018). The importance of understanding cultural vocabulary in speaking for tour guides not only has an impact on the tourist experience, but also on the sustainability of local culture. By strengthening tour guides' understanding of Balinese culture, it is hoped that tourists can encourage a deeper appreciation for this cultural heritage (Dewi 2023).

Competent tour guides play a central role in creating positive experiences for visitors at a tourist attraction (Jumail, Par, and Par 2014). The competence of a tour guide is not only limited to in-depth knowledge of tourist attractions, but also includes the ability to communicate this information effectively to the general public. In-depth knowledge about tourist attractions, including the history, culture and uniqueness of the place, is the main foundation in providing valuable experiences to visitors (Ma'rifah and Suryadarma 2015).

Apart from that, public speaking or public speaking skills are also an important aspect of a tour guide's skills. Being able to convey information clearly, interestingly and convincingly can increase the attractiveness of the tourist experience (Prameswari and Makhasi 2020). A tour guide who has good public speaking skills can build an emotional connection with the audience, explain complex concepts in a way that is easy to understand, and answer questions confidently.

Developing tour guide competency involves increasing knowledge about tourist attractions as well as mastering public speaking skills. Through a combination of the two, tour guides can not only provide accurate and interesting information, but also create a friendly and entertaining atmosphere (Rodjinandri and Supriadi 2016). This is the key to ensuring that visitors not only leave tourist attractions with deeper knowledge, but also with positive impressions that they will remember on each of their tourist trips (Kristanti 2019).

There fore, it is important to develop speaking teaching materials that focus on understanding cultural terms especially for students in Tourism department. The students who are preparing as professional tour guides requires not only skill but also how they can deliver information about culture to the guests. This teaching material will not only increase their knowledge about tourist destinations, but also provide in-depth insight into vocabulary related to aspects of Balinese culture (Mahagangga & Nugroho, 2017). The students who have a better understanding of local cultural terms can communicate information more authentically and with rich meaning to visitors (Rusmiati, Malihah, and Andari 2022).

In this context, the teaching materials developed will emphasize the importance of cultural vocabulary as a key element in conveying engaging and in-depth information. This will not only give students' confidence in public speaking, but also create a more memorable tourism experience for visitors (Saepudin 2014). By understanding cultural vocabulary, the students can depict local stories more vividly, enriching their interactions with tourists, and ultimately, making a positive contribution to the promotion and maintenance of Bali's cultural heritage (Sukmawan, Firdaus, and Ramadhani 2022). With this teaching material, it is hoped that tour guides can become effective ambassadors in conveying the charm of Balinese culture to the world, creating a deeper connection between tourists and the rich culture that Bali has.

This research aims to develop speaking teaching materials that focus on understanding cultural terms for students in Tourism department. The main goal is to improve the communication skills of students in conveying cultural information to visitors more authentically and in depth as a professional tour guide. The benefits of this research involve improving the quality of tourist

experiences, more effective promotion of Bali's cultural riches, and positive contributions to the preservation of local cultural heritage. With this teaching material, it is hoped that tour guides can provide a more memorable tourism experience, enrich tourists' understanding of Balinese culture, and support efforts to preserve unique and valuable cultural riches.

2. Literature Review

1) Development of Teaching Materials

Development is translating product specifications into physical form (Kosasih 2021). Moreover, she states that "development can be interpreted as the act of providing something from unavailable to available or making improvements to something that is available to make it more suitable, more effective and more efficient". Furthermore, regarding the development of teaching materials, it is stated that the development of teaching materials is a systematic process of identifying, developing, evaluating content and learning strategies which are directed at achieving learning goals more effectively and more efficiently.

The development of this teaching material has a purpose. Because, this goal is very influential as a whole in the development of content, materials and teaching materials themselves. According to (Sadjati 2012) conveys the above objectives through the following quote: The development of teaching materials has planned objectives, including: preparing learning activities in various situations so that they can take place optimally (1), increasing teacher motivation to manage teaching and learning activities (2), and preparing teaching and learning activities by filling in materials Always new material, presented in new ways and implemented with new learning strategies.

In developing materials, teachers do not always have to produce materials from a scratch. As states, material development is not only a process producing materials for language learning, but it can also be an integral process of adapting, designing, producing, exploiting, and researching (Tomlinson 2011). Furthermore, he adds that materials development also involves the study of how to design, implement, and evaluate the materials. It is also a practical undertaking which means that the process of materials development involves not only teachers as the materials developers, but also learners. Both of them are the sources of language input as they take part in making use of sources to promote language learning.

2) Speaking ability

Speaking ability is the ability to pronounce articulate sounds or words to express, state and convey thoughts, ideas and feelings. Speaking is a system of signs that can be heard (audible) and visible (visible) that utilizes a number of muscles and muscle tissue of the human body for the purpose and purpose of combined ideas (Beta 2019). A different thing was stated by that speaking ability is the ability to say sentences to express, express, convey thoughts, ideas and feelings (Setyonegoro 2013). Listeners receive information through a series of tones, pressure and joint placement. If done face to face, hand movements and facial expressions also play a role.

The ability to speak is an indicator of a child's overall development. Because the ability to speak is sensitive to delays or damage to other systems because it involves cognitive abilities, sensory motor skills, psychology, emotions and the environment around the child. A child will not be able to speak without support from his environment (Nurlaelah and Sakkir 2020). From the opinions above, it can be concluded that speaking ability is the ability to express, state and convey ideas, thoughts, thoughts or feelings to other people using spoken language that can be understood by other people. Activities

that children can do are interacting and communicating with the people around them so that they can train children to be skilled at speaking.

3) *Tour guide*

We can learn the meaning of a tour guide from the function of his duties and responsibilities in bringing groups of tourists. From the tour operator's point of view, where a tour guide works, he is none other than an employee who is assigned to carry out guiding (guiding) for groups of tourists who buy tour packages from the tour operator concerned. In general, the definition of a tour guide is a person who works as a guide who accompanies tourists on a tourist trip (tour) visit to see and witness tourist objects and attractions at a particular destination (Yoeti 2013). Guiding Technique states: "Tour Guide is a person employed either by the traveler, a travel agency or any other tourist organization, to inform, direct and advise the tourist organization, to inform, direct and advise the tourist before and during their short visits" (Amato 2021).

From several definitions of a tour guide, it can be defined that a tour guide is a person whose job is to provide guidance, information and instructions about attractions or destinations. The job of guiding tourists gives the impression of a job that is luxurious and enjoyable with large rewards, even though tour guide is a profession (get decent pay for your abilities) which is unique, because this profession requires language skills (as required), being able to interact with tourists, having extensive knowledge, being flexible, full of understanding and maturity of thinking as well as excellent health/physical/physical strength.

4) *ADDIE Model*

According to (Molenda 2015), ADDIE model is an instructional design which employs process-based approach to develop instructional materials. In their study, (Wang and Hsu 2008) stated that as an instructional design, ADDIE model was adopted so that learners would improve their knowledge and skills. As language teaching contains of a set of instructional materials, materials developers should determine the phases of producing or developing the materials.

(Peterson 2003)states that adopting ADDIE model in a course is beneficial as it is more learner-centered rather than teacher- centered. From the very beginning of its stages (analysis and design), learners who will take the course are highly considered. In the development phase, it is also based on learners' needs.

Besides, in its implementation and evaluation, learners are highly involved to measure the effectiveness of the materials. Further, Peterson (2003) asserts that ADDIE model can be applied in various teaching contexts which employ instructional design. ADDIE model consists of 5 steps, namely: 1) Analysis, 2) Design, 3) Development, 4) Implementation, and 5) Evaluation.

3. Materials and Methods

This research is Research and Development (R&D) with Exploratory Mixed Method using ADDIE model. ADDIE consist of five steps namely 1) Analysis, 2) Design, 3) Development, 4) Implementation, and 5) Evaluation. The participants involved in this study were 120 students and 3 English lecturers of Tourism Department. The data collected through distributed questionnaire to the students and interview to the lecturers. Furthermore, ADDIE model will explained briefly as follow:

Figure 1. ADDIE Model

- 1). Analyze : the research conducted need analysis in order to find out the learners' need. In this step, the questionnaires were distributed to the students, the materials was analysed based on curriculum to find out the learners' outcomes and the courses offered as the content of the coursebook would be made in line with the courses of the field of study. And the interview was conducted to the English lecturers.
- 2). Design : the course and the materials were designed based on the data from interview and the result of questionnaire. The design of the course is reflected in the syllabus which covers several aspects, such as course description, course goals, learning objectives, materials, speaking activities, and assessment.
- 3). Development : the coursebook was developed after setting the syllabus. There were three major resources used in developing coursebook, including online resources, printed coursebooks, and self-made materials. The online resources and printed coursebooks were adapted by adding, reducing, or changing
- 4) Implementation : the book designed was implemented in English class for 120 students in Tourism Department.
- 5) Evaluation : was done by collecting information concerning the use of the developed coursebook through questionnaire and interviews. The data from the interviews were used to support the questionnaires data as well as to seek suggestions for the improvement of the developed material. In shorts, the steps in conducting this research are shown in Figure 1

4. Results and Discussion

Development of speaking teaching materials for tour guides by emphasizing the understanding of cultural terms using ADDIE model. Therefore, the findings will revolve around materials were developed by using that model. Specifically, the explanation can be described as follows:

a. Analyze

ADDIE model provides valuable guidance in developing speaking teaching materials, which can be applied effectively in the context of teaching tour guides with a focus on understanding Balinese cultural vocabulary. First of all, need analysis was conducted by interviewing the English lecturers and analyzing the current materials. The questionnaire also distributed to the

students in English class. This needs analysis is important since the materials that highly accommodate the learners' needs. The result of questionnaire showed that the current materials and the students' need to find out the gap and able to design the appropriate materials. Students' need was analyzed using Target Situational Analysis by Hutchinson and Waters (1987) that divide into three part namely necessity, lack and want which obtained from the result of questionnaire distributed to the students.

<i>Questions</i>	<i>Answer</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>The most important skill as a tour guide</i>	<i>a listening</i>	52	48,6
	<i>b reading</i>	23	21,5
	<i>c speaking</i>	102	95,3
	<i>d writing</i>	22	20,6
<i>Problems in speaking</i>	<i>a less vocabularies of culture in speaking English</i>	54	50,5
	<i>b fear in making mistakes in speaking English</i>	54	50,5
	<i>c unfamiliar vocabulary in tourism</i>	31	29
	<i>d difficult in pronouncing the words</i>	15	14
<i>Expectation of learning experience</i>	<i>a group work</i>	26	21,6
	<i>b role play</i>	67	55,8
	<i>c debate</i>	10	8,3
	<i>d presentation</i>	17	14

Table 1. The result of Need Analysis

The result of need analysis was the urgency for inserting cultural terms in teaching materials in order to develop speaking ability. The necessity of speaking ability showed 95,3 % should be developed for students in English subject and the others skills will supported. The percentage of problems in speaking indicated the limited vocabularies provided in teaching materials. 50,5% showed that students' problems in explaining vocabulary in English. (Alqahtani 2015) also claimed that vocabulary knowledge is a central component of communicative competence because limited vocabulary impedes successful communication. Therefore, vocabulary is crucial and mandated to be explicitly written in speaking material books.

The current materials did not provide sufficient topic which is related to Balinese culture. It is very challenging for the students who are not familiar with Balinese culture. In addition, tourists will get a deeper and more memorable experience when directed by a guide who is able to better communicate the richness of Balinese culture. A tour guide can be introduced to a wider range of cultural nuances and details, which will enrich their understanding and, in turn, improve the quality of information delivery to tourist.

b. Design

In this step, the material was designed based on the result of need analysis. According to (Graves and Xu 2000) the tangible results of materials development process are the course and the coursebook. The materials contains topics of tour guide situations in which useful expressions and terms are introduced and practiced. The result of analysis require the materials to insert cultural terms to develop speaking ability. The materials was designed using topic based which refers to an approach that organizes learning around specific themes or topics rather than following a strictly linear or subject-based structure. In a topic-based, the content is designed

and delivered based on real-world themes or issues, allowing students to explore and understand concepts in a more integrated and holistic manner. The course materials can be designed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Culture based Material Design

Based on figure 2, the cultural terms that classified inserted into sub topics. The lesson will be divided into 4 major sub topics, each of which consist of some cultural term classification. (Newmark 1988) classified cultural terms into 5 types namely ecology, social culture, material culture, tradition, gesture and habit. It should be noted the distribution of cultural terms in each unit is different since the focus is on what language skills can best accommodate the achievement of learning objectives. To engage students with the subtopic, the materials provide illustration of the certain culture completed with pictures to guide students in communication skills. Vocabulary is essential for the process of acquiring a language, the teaching vocabulary should be contextual. The source of text are taken, selected and adapted from existing course and combined with internet resources. It accords with (Nielsen et al. 2019), who report that English learners in intercultural instruction are making an intimate connection between cultural sensitivity, social structures, and social-emotional competencies.

c. Development

The development of teaching materials that pay attention to eliminating unnecessary information and emphasizing key elements, it is hoped that students can better assimilate and convey Balinese cultural vocabulary. A thoughtful process of discarding will enhance the teaching material, making it more concise and focused, and ensuring that every word and concept taught has maximum impact on the students' speaking experience. Thus, the discarding stage in

developing teaching materials becomes an essential step in increasing the effectiveness of tour guide communication in the Balinese cultural context.

In this stage, choosing simple and common words and phrases can help create more effective communication. In this way, students can more smoothly and clearly communicate about cultural terms with the tourists from various backgrounds, increasing mutual acceptance and understanding. The process of development may also involve the use of pictures, diagrams, or other visual materials to aid understanding. Visualization can strengthen teaching and help students convey Balinese cultural concepts more directly and clearly. Students can use these visual materials as a supporting tool to better explain cultural vocabulary based on context and meaning contained in each word.

Furthermore, it required to arrange activities based on a particular context or theme. The purpose is create teaching materials more structured guidance for students in understanding and conveying Balinese cultural vocabulary. By considering sequencing variations, this teaching material will create a more effective learning environment and make it easier for tour guides to assimilate and communicate information to visitors. In the assessment of the development of this material, there will be two experts and one practitioner who assesses the material developed. They are the experts in English teaching materials and also the expert in English guiding. To determine the quality of the material should be developed, the first inspection process, namely checking the checklist, is left to the experts. Material evaluation on the checklist based on good ESP material criteria.

d. *Implementation*

After developing the designed materials, the next step is implementation. In this implementation step, the materials were used by all students in tourism department. Here, the material as the main resource in learning English for tour guide.

e. *Evaluation*

The evaluation of the materials on the checklist was based on the criteria of good ESP materials suggested by (Litz 2005); (Hutchinson and Waters 1987); (Tomlinson 2011). After developing the materials English for tour guide, it was necessary to evaluate the materials to assess whether it was appropriate for tourism students or not. The evaluation involved the students of tourism department and lecturers as users which was given questionnaire related to the use of materials. The questionnaire were distributed in the last meeting since it intends to get evaluation which is based on students vivid recall on their use of developed material. Students answer each statement in questionnaire which was categorized into four major areas, namely language, content, task, and learning focus (Tomlinson, 2009). The results of this evaluation were very important in the research process because this evaluation was the finals step carried out to create the contextual product and ready to use for students at improving speaking ability (Lapele 2019).

Components of evaluation	Statement	Responds (%)
<i>Language</i>	The materials contain adequate speaking skills related to tour guide	86
	The materials contain useful expressions related to speaking skill as tour guide	88

<i>Content</i>	The topics are related to speaking skills related to tour guide	90
<i>Task</i>	The task in the textbook are varied	83
	The task provide exercise to develop speaking ability	84
	The task was arranged from easy to complex	85
<i>Learning and Students</i>	The textbook promotes interaction among students.	82
	The textbook can develop speaking ability	85
<i>Visuals</i>	Image/ Illustration in the textbook are appropriate with topics	80
	Image/Illustration in the textbook are interesting	83
	Image/ illustration in the textbook motivate the students to learn	85

Table 2. Result of evaluation

The result of evaluation showed that the material are principally provide positive contribution especially speaking ability. In terms of language, students comfortable with the materials because it allows the students to acquire language skills and topics relevant to their subject of study. Based on the result on table 2, the content of the materials is appropriate with the topic, situations and knowledge. A similar response also derived from not only the object being evaluated (the materials) but also the affective and interpersonal interactions among the users. The users agree that the materials is interesting and able to encourage them to learn. Self-confidents significantly influenced the students accomplish language skill (Nurhayati and Hartono 2023). The result, the students responds positive to the English material. The effective aspect of learning of a foreign language should be considered because it impacts show much input students can gain (Arnold 2020).

The design of culture-based materials is organized based on language functions that become learning outcomes integrated with cultural concepts. Based on the explanation above and also the findings of the need's analysis of English teaching materials for tour guides, further teaching materials will be developed using the theory of Hutchinson and Waters (1987) which is guided by input, content (focus content), language focus, and tasks. These four components have an interrelated relationship in developing teaching materials. The input given in one topic must be in line with the content, language focus and also the tasks given to students based on the learning objectives. Furthermore, students can learn English skills through ELT materials incorporating local cultural topics in textbooks. It is also for improving critical thinking (Kusumoto 2018).

5. Conclusion

The development of English materials was designed using ADDIE model which consists of five steps. Those steps are analyze, design, development, implementation and evaluation. The result from analysis is very significant in developing material English for tour guide. Need analysis showed that the material required to explore vocabularies about culture. There are cultural terms classified and integrated into the topics. The result showed that the development of English for tour guide material provide benefit for students to improve speaking ability. The students respond positively to the materials designed which encourage them to learn English based on context.

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References

- Alqahtani, Mofareh. 2015. "The Importance of Vocabulary in Language Learning and How to Be Taught." *International journal of teaching and education* 3(3): 21–34.
- Amato, Ettore. 2021. *Manual for Guiding Techniques*. Sanata Dharma University Press.
- Arnold, Jane. 2020. "Affective Factors and Language Learning." *Language education and emotions: Research into emotions and language learners, language teachers and educational processes*: 18–33.
- Beta, Pancana. 2019. "Peningkatan Keterampilan Berbicara Melalui Metode Bermain Peran." *Cokroaminoto Journal of Primary Education* 2(2): 48–52.
- Dewi, Ni Putu Sasmika. 2023. "Pentingnya Penguasaan Bahasa Asing Sebagai Salah Satu Pendukung Faktor Utama Industri Pariwisata." *Paryatana: Jurnal Pariwisata Budaya dan Keagamaan* 2(1): 153–62.
- Graves, Kathleen, and Shisheng Xu. 2000. *Designing Language Courses: A Guide for Teachers*. Heinle & Heinle Boston, MA.
- Hutchinson, Tom, and Alan Waters. 1987. *English for Specific Purposes*. Cambridge university press.
- Jumail, Mohamad, S S T Par, and M Par. 2014. *Teknik Pemanduan Wisata*. Penerbit Andi.
- Kosasih, E. 2021. *Pengembangan Bahan Ajar*. Bumi Aksara.
- Kristanti, Lusiana. 2019. "Media Cue Card Untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Berbicara Siswa Sebagai Pramuwisata Dalam Mendeskripsikan Tempat Wisata Di Kalimantan Barat Untuk Kelas X UPW Smk Negeri 1 Pontianak." *Jurnal Guru Dikmen dan Dikus* 2(2): 54–66.
- Kusumoto, Yoko. 2018. "Enhancing Critical Thinking through Active Learning." *Language Learning in Higher Education* 8(1): 45–63.
- Lapele, Fitria. 2019. "Need Analysis on the Material Development of Teaching ESP Speaking." *ETERNAL (English, Teaching, Learning, and Research Journal)* 5(2): 336–49.
- Litz, David R A. 2005. "Textbook Evaluation and ELT Management: A South Korean Case Study." *Asian EFL journal* 48(1): 1–53.
- Ma'rifah, Destri Ratna, and I Gusti Putu Suryadarma. 2015. "Penyusunan Panduan Edutourism Hutan Wisata Tlogo Nirmolo Guna Memunculkan Karakter Peserta Didik Kelas X." *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan IPA* 1(2): 126–37.

*Cultural Terms in Need Analysis of English for Tour Guiding
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- Mahagangga, I Gusti Agung Oka, and SAPTONO NUGROHO. 2017. *Pemahaman Lintas Budaya Dalam Kepariwisata*. Cakra Press bekerja sama dengan Fakultas Pariwisata, Universitas Udayana.
- Molenda, Michael. 2015. "In Search of the Elusive ADDIE Model." *Performance improvement* 54(2): 40–42.
- Newmark, Peter. 1988. *66 A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice hall New York.
- Nielsen, Birgitte Lund et al. 2019. "Social, Emotional and Intercultural Competencies: A Literature Review with a Particular Focus on the School Staff." *European Journal of Teacher Education* 42(3): 410–28.
- Nurazizah, Ghoitsa Rohmah. 2021. "Pelatihan Pemanduan Wisata Berbahasa Isyarat Melalui Video Virtual Tour Bagi Kelompok Penggerak Pariwisata Desa Wisata Alamendah." *Dinamisia: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat* 5(4).
- Nurhayati, Siti, and Rudi Hartono. 2023. "Comparing the Effectiveness of Multitask Role-Play and Traditional Technique in Teaching Speaking to Students with Different Self-Confident Levels." *English Education Journal* 13(1): 1–11.
- Nurlaelah, Nurlaelah, and Geminastiti Sakkir. 2020. "Model Pembelajaran Respons Verbal Dalam Kemampuan Berbicara." *Edumaspul: Jurnal Pendidikan* 4(1): 113–22.
- Peterson, Christine. 2003. "Bringing ADDIE to Life: Instructional Design at Its Best." *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia* 12(3): 227–41.
- Prameswari, Mutiara Chartika, and Ghifari Yuristiadhi Masyhari Makhasi. 2020. "Penilaian Wisatawan Asing Atas Kemampuan Bahasa Inggris Mahasiswa Dan Pelajar Magang Sebagai Pemandu Wisata Di Taman Wisata Candi Prambanan." *JLA (Jurnal Lingua Applicata)* 4(1): 27.
- Rodjinandri, N, and Bambang Supriadi. 2016. "Kompetensi Pendampingan Pemandu Wisata Lokal Sebagai Developers of People." *Jurnal Pariwisata Pesona.[Online]* 2(1): 72–86.
- Rusmiati, Debi, Elly Malihah, and Rini Andari. 2022. "Peran Pemandu Wisata Dalam Pariwisata Pendidikan." *Jurnal Inovasi Penelitian* 3(2): 4765–74.
- Sadjati, Ida Malati. 2012. "Pengembangan Bahan Ajar."
- Saepudin, Saepudin. 2014. "An Introduction to English Learning and Teaching Methodology."
- Setyonegoro, Agus. 2013. "Hakikat, Alasan, Dan Tujuan Berbicara (Dasar Pembangun Kemampuan Berbicara Mahasiswa)." *Pena: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra* 2(2).
- Subhiksu, Ida Bagus Kade, and Gusti Bagus Rai Utama. 2018. *Daya Tarik Wisata Museum Sejarah Dan Perkembangannya Di Ubud Bali*. Deepublish.
- Sukmawan, Sony, Elvin Nuril Firdaus, and Asri Kamila Ramadhani. 2022. *Mendaras Puja, Mengemas*

Tamasya. Universitas Brawijaya Press.

Suweta, I Made. 2020. "Kebudayaan Bali Dalam Konteks Pengembangan Pariwisata Budaya." *Cultoure: Jurnal Ilmiah Pariwisata Budaya Hindu* 1(1): 1-14.

Tomlinson, Brian. 2011. *Materials Development in Language Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.

Wang, Shiang-Kwei, and Hui-Yin Hsu. 2008. "Using ADDIE Model to Design Second Life Activities for Online Learners." In *E-Learn: World Conference on e-Learning in Corporate, Government, Healthcare, and Higher Education*, Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE), 2045-50.

Yoeti, Oka A. 2013. "Pemasaran Pariwisata, Edisi Revisi." *Bandung: CV Angkasa*.